

CERTIFICATE

OF APRECIATION

SHARQ FALSAFASI

Ismailova Gulsara Jalgasbaevna

FEATURES OF HUMAN PSYCHOLOGY IN THE PROCESS
OF SOCIALIZATION

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANDI

